

Recommended citation: Deckert, C. (2018). Creative Heuristics in Engineering Education. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 724-731). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672675.

Creative Heuristics in Engineering Education

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Conference Key Areas: Teaching Creativity & Innovation

Keywords: Creativity, Invention, Heuristics

INTRODUCTION

Creativity is one of the key skills of the 21st century. This importance is reflected in the educational policy documents of many countries from Europe, America, Australia and East Asia [1]. Creativity also plays an important role in engineering, and engineering can be viewed as a special case of a more general process of creative problem solving [2].

However, many current curricula in engineering education do not seem to adequately incorporate creativity. An analysis of module descriptions at three leading German technical universities shows that the skills necessary for generating original ideas are absent from most subjects taught [3]. This seems to be especially so for study programs in engineering. A survey amongst students from the three general academic areas engineering, sciences and humanities at the University of Connecticut shows that there are far more absent creativity criteria in engineering than in the other areas [4]. This could mean that prospective engineers are not well educated in creativity skills and that the students' creative self-concepts even suffer from study programs in engineering. A cross-sectional study at a large mid-Atlantic university shows no change in creative self-efficacy for first-year and senior engineering students. Furthermore, it shows lower creative identity and lower expectations for creative results in senior students with the strongest decline in the group of female students [5].

Apart from the problems of over-specialization and focus on factual knowledge, Cropley [2] sees a main problem in engineering in a lack of knowledge about creativity. There often seems to be no consistent definition of creativity and no clear understanding of the underlying psychological principles enabling creativity in engineering. This coincides with the author's

observation that the focus of creativity in engineering is usually on creativity techniques such as brainstorming or TRIZ/TIPS (Theory of Inventive Problem Solving) without a clear understanding of how these techniques work and why. However, the more intuitive creativity techniques such as brainstorming are often too broad for engineering problems as they mainly rely on association, while the more analytical approaches such as TRIZ are focused on invention, but are very complicated and tend to overwhelm the engineering students.

The paper proposes the use of heuristics containing process rules for engineering education in creativity, as they are useful in highly uncertain environments, easy to learn and provide direction and instruction for novice engineers. A literature analysis of existing concepts in creative problem solving and insight psychology is conducted to find the main heuristic principles of creative problem solving. Moreover, a qualitative meta-analysis of existing collections of heuristics in invention from historical analysis, inventor insights or principles underlying creativity techniques provides useful creative heuristics. As a result, the paper develops a framework for creative heuristics in engineering with four main principles. The framework contains a collection of creative heuristics in engineering allocated to the main principles and can be used in engineering education to support students in inventive projects.

1 CREATIVE PRODUCTS AND PROBLEMS IN ENGINEERING

The standard definition of creativity includes the two components originality and effectiveness [6]. On the one hand, a creative product should have novel attributes, which makes it unusual, unexpected or even inconceivable. On the other hand, a creative product should also fulfil a certain need or solve a given problem and be in some form useful, appropriate or valuable.

This is especially so for the products of engineering. In this regard, Cropley & Cropley [7] use the term “functional creativity” to describe the creativity necessary for industrial products such as engineered items or manufactured consumer goods. The focus of functional creativity is on the useful purpose of novel products, i.e. a novel product must fulfil its intended need. Thus, effectiveness is more important than originality for functional creativity.

Creative problems in engineering are described as either insight problems or inventive problems. Insight problems usually lead to a fixation or impasse blocking the route to a better solution [8]. An inventive problem can be defined as a “problem containing a contradiction in the form of incompatible requirements and/or properties [...] that cannot be solved by adequate methods and means” [9]. Both insight and inventive problems cannot be solved analytically but require new approaches to overcome either the impasse or the contradiction.

According to Perkins [10] problem spaces which require a creative solution have four characteristics: They offer a wide range of possible solutions with only a few fruitful ones (Rarity). Those fruitful solutions usually lie isolated or semi-isolated (Isolation) without any obvious connection or clues for a promising direction (Plateau). This makes it hard to depart from existing solutions, so that inventors are often stuck with solutions offering false promises (Oasis). In this situation, simple rules or principles can help to find promising target gradients to initiate a search direction for a better solution and overcome the fixation on current solutions.

In a study of inventors, Perkins [10] finds that inventors tend to work in the middle of the continuum between sheer chance and safe bet. This means that they usually work on problems where they see at least a systematized chance of success or even a fair to good bet. It does not mean that inventors do not exploit chance occurrences along the way, as in fact they often do. It rather means that inventors seem to make use of “general principles underlying invention” [11], which will be explored in the following sections.

2 CREATIVE HEURISTICS

In the scientific literature, two kinds of definition of the term “heuristics” can be distinguished. One kind of definition is from the field of decision-making, and signifies rules of thumb to distil the most important information of a situation for the given choice. This approach often leads to useful solutions for complex problems under high uncertainty, but not necessarily to the best or optimum solution [12]. In the field of decision-making, there is often a clear rational choice to be favoured, and the discovered heuristics have a descriptive character.

The other kind of definition is from the field of problem solving and creativity. In this field, a heuristic can be described as “a strategy or rule of thumb for generating ideas or for solving problems” [11]. These heuristics can be derived by analysing the work of inventors and need to be of a medium generality, so that they are both meaningful and applicable for different kinds of problems [13]. In the field of problem solving, there is usually an open-ended problem situation, in which the targets are not always clear and there is no obvious rational solution. This means that these heuristics are prescriptive and indicate a promising search direction to the inventor. However, due to their medium generality they do not deliver a ready-made solution. “Heuristic reasoning is reasoning not regarded as final and strict but as provisional and plausible only, whose purpose is to discover the solution of the present problem” [13]. Heuristics for creative problem solving are called creative heuristics in this paper.

3 FRAMEWORK OF CREATIVE HEURISTICS

The qualitative meta-analysis focuses on existing collections of heuristics from the field of technical invention. The main research method is a qualitative content analysis. For this, a category system for the classification of heuristics is developed. The development of the category system is theory-driven and deduced from existing literature in the fields of creativity, insight psychology and heuristic problem solving. An overview of the main concepts distinguishing different heuristic principles is given in table 1. Other concepts – not mentioned in this paper – often focus on one single principle, e.g. association or combination.

One basic concept of creative problem solving is lateral thinking. Lateral thinking is described by de Bono [14] as a deliberate and practical process related to insight, creativity and humour. The target of lateral thinking is to restructure insights or fixed mental patterns. The two basic principles of lateral thinking are the generation of alternatives and the challenging of assumptions. With regard to insight problems, Klein [15] proposes a Triple Path Model for insights characterized by different activities. These activities are not only different, but partly contradictory. While the Contradiction Path builds on a weak assumption against conventional wisdom, the Creative Desperation Path eliminates the weak assumption to generate a new solution, and the Connection Path generates a completely new assumption by using coincidences or curiosity to connect different elements in a new way. A prominent categorization of creativity techniques is the structure proposed by Geschka and colleagues [16]. The structure is based on the main underlying idea-generating principles of the techniques, which enable the user to break out of fixed mental routines. The principles distinguished are free association, structured association, configuration, confrontation and imagination. Another set of heuristics to solve various problems called “Modern Heuristics” is proposed by Polya [13]. Apart from analogy and combination, this set of concept contains many rules to restructure the problem, i.e. to vary the problem, to specialize or generalize the problem or to add auxiliary elements or problems.

Table 1. Concepts of Heuristic Principles

Lateral thinking [14]	Paths to insights [15]	Idea-generating principles of creativity techniques [16]	Modern heuristics [13]
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of alternatives • Challenging of assumptions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contradiction • Connection, coincidence, curiosity • Creative desperation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free association • Structured association • Configuration • Confrontation • Imagination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variation of the problem • Decomposing and recombining • Generalization • Specialisation • Analogy • Auxiliary elements • Auxiliary problem

From the existing concepts of heuristic principles a framework is developed which serves as a category system for the content analysis (see figure 1). The basis of the framework is the distinction of generating alternatives and challenging assumption by de Bono [14]. Additionally the elements of reframing the problem and fine-tuning the solution are added.

Reframing the problem is a necessary element in the creative problem solving process and specifically addressed in the approach by Polya [13]. It can be achieved by generalizing or specialising the problem, e.g. moving from the level of raw material to the level of final product in product development. Furthermore, reframing of the problem can be achieved by broadening the scope through auxiliary problems or elements. In the case of product development, this could mean focussing on the configuration of the business model or the customer experience instead of on the product offering or it could mean to include further elements such as packaging design or the design of complementary products.

The generation of alternatives can be achieved by “Variabilization & Configuration” and by “Combination & Separation”. Confrontation is incorporated in the connection path of Klein [15] and is an idea-generating principle of creativity techniques [16]. Furthermore the principle of variabilization is a central feature of many inventive heuristics such as those found in [11]. The principle of combination is mentioned in all of the described concepts of principles. Although it is not directly mentioned as an idea-generating principle of creativity techniques, it is implicitly included in the principle of configuration as the examples of creativity techniques in this category mentioned in [16] also use combinatorial principles, e.g. Morphological Box.

Challenging assumptions can be achieved by “Contradiction & Confrontation” and by “Imagination & Visualization”. Contradiction is a central feature of an inventive problem as defined in the inventive approach of TRIZ/TIPS and is an idea-generating principle of creativity techniques. The principle includes both the contradiction path and the creative desperation path of Klein [15] where either a weak assumption is discarded or a weak assumption is used to build a new insight and usually a conventional assumption is discarded. So both of these paths are about discarding unnecessary or inadequate assumptions. Imagination is mentioned as one of the idea-generating principles by Geschka and Zirm [16] and is reported by many

inventors as a central approach, amongst them famous and often-cited accounts of August Kekulé, Albert Einstein and Nikola Tesla.

Fig. 1. Framework of Creative Heuristics [17]

The framework can be used as a toolbox with different phases. Usually the creative process starts with the definition of the problem, i.e. the first problem frame. Then ideas are generated via generating alternatives and challenging assumptions. If this approach is successful, the solution can then be fine-tuned. If the current solution is impractical, the problem solver can try to generate more ideas or to reframe the problem to find a better point of departure for a solution. In idea generation, the problem solver can switch between generating alternatives and challenging assumptions.

4 CREATIVE HEURISTICS IN INVENTION

Since heuristics are open to interpretation, a quantitative meta-analysis using statistics is not possible. For this reason, a qualitative content analysis is performed with the help of the developed category system. The content analysis proceeds as follows: Firstly, the determined heuristics are checked for medium generality. This means that each rule has to be specific enough to facilitate a concrete search direction, while simultaneously being broad enough to cover problems in several engineering subject matters. After that, the heuristic rule has to be allocated to a heuristic principle in the developed framework and compared with already allocated heuristics. If an overlap exists, the new rule has to be either integrated into the existing rule or discarded as a redundant rule. The rules come from collections of heuristics in literature on invention such as the collections by Weber and colleagues (e.g. [11], [18]). Additionally, idea checklists such as SCAMPER (acronym for Substitute, Combine, Adapt, Modify, Put to another use, Eliminate, Reverse) or the inventive principles by TRIZ/TIPS were analysed. Table 2 gives an overview over the determined heuristics.

Heuristics of invention offer some very specific rules for creative solutions. E.g. the Inverse Heuristic where an invention is joined with its inverse function seems to be a very powerful heuristic often used by inventors. Examples of products incorporating this heuristic are the claw hammer or the pencil with erasure, i.e. products that can both do and undo an operation. However, some inventive heuristics are of a more general type such as "Vary the variable"

which can be used in its broad form or which can be broken down into more specific sub-rules such the Repeated-Element-Heuristic (repeat an interesting component) [11].

Idea checklists often offer only very broad and unspecific rules such as SCAMPER. A notable exception are the 40 inventive principles offered by TRIZ/TIPS. The allocation of the TRIZ principles in the heuristic framework is problematic as these principles include medium generality heuristics (e.g. Universality) as well as very specific heuristics (e.g. Mechanical Vibration). Furthermore, they include considerable overlap to heuristics, which can also be used for generating alternatives (e.g. Segmentation) [9]. However, the TRIZ principles can be condensed to a few main actions, which are included in the collection, and it seems to be a useful approach to try to find the main contradiction of the inventive problem.

Table 2. Creative Heuristics [17]

Generation of alternatives		Challenging assumptions	
Variabilization & Configuration	Combination & Separation	Contradiction & Confrontation	Imagination & Visualization
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vary the variables • Find a trajectory of evaluation function • Add relevant features • Package relevant features • Improve the human interface • Delete irrelevant features • Abstract and transform (scale, dimensionality, matching) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider the negative or inverse • Combine inventions with complementary or emergent qualities • Combine to eliminate redundancy • Interpolate and extrapolate • Find a new purpose • Separate and recombine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kill the product • Reverse the assumption • Force a connection (visual or verbal) • Describe the ideal solution • Find the main contradiction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take a picture of the problem • Try to become the problem • Visualize or sketch the ideal solution • Change the perspective • Prototype the (ideal) solution

The creative heuristics collected from the literature are displayed in table 2. For a full description of the heuristics and the analysed sources, see [17]. As the framework is open-ended, further heuristics can be added to complement the framework.

5 SUMMARY AND FURTHER APPLICATION

The paper at hand developed a framework of creative heuristics for engineering with four main principles. The framework contains a collection of creative heuristics for the generation of alternatives and challenging assumptions in the process of invention. The heuristics are suitable for the use in engineering education. Advantages of creative heuristics in comparison to creativity techniques are that they are both easy to understand and easy to apply. It is, however, advisable to explain the heuristics to the students by using examples of products incorporating one or more of the rules.

The framework was already used in a master course on innovation and technology management with a practical part. In the practical part of the course, the students have to re-design an everyday object. That means that they have to find a flaw or dysfunction of an already existing product, which corresponds to mess finding in the creative problem solving process, and translate this mess into a concrete problem. Then they solve the problem using creativity techniques or creative heuristics, thus correcting the flaw – a classical engineering task. This first test elicited positive feedback concerning the heuristics, albeit the approach has not been evaluated on a systematic basis, yet. For this, the students will be randomly assigned to groups who solve their problems with either creative heuristics or creativity techniques in the next course, and the results will be rated with regard to creativity by experienced engineers. Furthermore, the learning outcome will be evaluated by letting the students rate the approaches.

A further measure is to complement the framework and to rank the heuristics according to usefulness or effectiveness. To achieve this, interviews with inventors are going to be conducted in cooperation with two German non-profit organizations dedicated to creativity and invention – the German Inventors Association and the German Association for Creativity.

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